

Safety Platform for Emergency vACcines

Updated Landscape Analysis for
Priority List of Adverse events of special interest:
for MERS

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DOCUMENT INFORMATION

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Description of the deliverable	This deliverable provides the methods and results of an updated landscape analysis and priority list of potential adverse events of special interest relevant to MERS vaccine trials
Key words	Guidance document, AESI list, MERS, Middle East Respiratory Syndrome, Toolbox

DEFINITIONS & ACRONYMS

ACE2	Angiotensin converting enzyme 2
ADEM	Acute disseminated encephalomyelitis
AEFI	Adverse Event Following Immunization
AESI	Adverse Event of Special Interest
AKI	Acute kidney injury
ARDS	Acute respiratory distress syndrome
AST	Aspartate transaminase
BC	Brighton Collaboration
CD	Case Definition
CG	Companion guide
CEPI	Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations
CIOMS	Council For International Organizations of Medical Sciences
CMV	Cytomegalovirus
CNS	Central nervous system
CoV	Coronavirus
DIC	Disseminated intravascular coagulation
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic Acid
DPP4	Dipeptidyl-peptidase 4
EBV	Epstein Barr virus
ECMO	Extracorporeal membrane oxygenation
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
GBS	Guillain Barré syndrome
HIV	Human immunodeficiency virus
ICU	Intensive care unit
IQR	Interquartile range (difference between the 75 th and 25 th percentiles of the data)
IU	International unit
L	liter
LDH	Lactate dehydrogenase
MERS	Middle eastern respiratory syndrome
MI	Milliliters
MODS	Multiple organ dysfunction syndrome
MRI	Magnetic resonance imaging
MVA	Modified Vaccinia
OR	Odds ratio
95% CI	95% confidence interval

PaO ₂ :FiO ₂	Ratio of arterial pressure of arterial oxygen (measured in mm Hg) to inspired fraction of oxygen
Pg	picogram
PT	Prothrombin time
aPTT	Activated partial thromboplastin time
RT-PCR	Reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction
SARS	Severe acute respiratory syndrome
SD	Standard deviation
SPEAC	Safety Platform for Emergency vAccines
TFGH	Task force for global health
TTS	Thrombosis with thrombocytopenia syndrome
U	Unit
Ug	microgram
uL	microliter
VAED	Vaccine-associated enhanced disease
VITT	Vaccine-induced immune thrombocytopenia and thrombosis
WBC	White blood cell

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A key activity of SPEAC (Safety Platform for Emergency vACcines) has been to establish lists of adverse events of special interest (AESI) that have potential to occur during Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations (CEPI) funded clinical trials. The initial landscape analysis for MERS AESI was completed in conjunction with one for Lassa Fever on Feb 17, 2020, and was based on a non-systematic literature review of key articles. Two vaccine candidates funded by CEPI are in early phases (I or II) of development (IDT Biologika MERS vaccine – MVA; Oxford MERS – ChAdOx1). The primary objective of the update was to conduct a scoping review of literature published after the previous landscape analysis in order to determine whether any new AESI should be added to the previous AESI list for novel MERS vaccines. No new AESI were identified related to MERS virus disease, however, vaccine platform-associated AESI have been added: Thrombocytopenia with Thrombosis Syndrome (TTS) and Vaccine-Induced Thrombocytopenia (VITT) related to selected adenoviral vector vaccines; and myocarditis relevant to the MVA-vector vaccine platform. An updated version of the AESI list is included in Section V – Recommendations and Discussion. A new feature of the list is to include SPEAC recommendations regarding the listed AESI in terms of which should be prespecified in a clinical protocol (based on the vaccine platform or vector) as opposed to those which should be responded to, should any occur during a clinical trial, with a standard approach to investigation and review. All listed MERS AESIs have Brighton case definitions and SPEAC companion guides. The online version of the MERS AESI list has links to the case definitions and guides and can be found at the SPEAC website (<https://speacsafety.net/>).

1. Introduction

CEPI contracted the Brighton Collaboration (BC), through the Task Force for Global Health (TFGH), to harmonize safety assessment across CEPI funded vaccine development. Since inception, a key activity of SPEAC (Safety Platform for Emergency vACcines) has been to establish lists of adverse events of special interest (AESI) that have potential to occur during CEPI funded clinical trials.

Adverse events of special interest

An adverse event following immunization (AEFI) is defined as ‘any untoward medical occurrence which follows immunization, and which does not necessarily have a causal relationship with the usage of the vaccine. The adverse event may be any unfavorable or unintended sign, abnormal laboratory finding, symptom or disease.’¹

The source definition of ‘Adverse Event of Special Interest’ (AESI) as described in CIOMS VII² is:

“An adverse event of special interest (serious or non-serious) is one of scientific and medical concern specific to the sponsor’s product or program, for which ongoing monitoring and rapid communication by the investigator to the sponsor could be appropriate. Such an event might require further investigation to characterize and understand it. Depending on the nature of the event, rapid communication by the trial sponsor to other parties (e.g., regulators) might also be warranted.”

AESI can be specified in the Program Safety Analysis plan early in product development for safety planning, data collection, analysis and reporting on AESI data, and eventually form the base of AESI analysis in the Reporting and Analysis Plan.^{3,4} AESI may also be used to generate or retrieve background rates prior to vaccine launch and be incorporated in risk management plans.

Vaccine safety needs to be conducted across the entire life cycle of vaccine development, approval and use. It is essential that the approach is harmonized and standardized so that data are comparable across different studies and populations. Thus, while several if not most of the AESI identified as relevant to CEPI vaccine programs are likely to be rare events and may never occur in the context of a given trial, preparations must be made to maximize the utility of vaccine safety data so appropriate risk-benefit decisions can be made.

SPEAC uses 4 rationales for identifying potential AESI for a target disease and vaccine candidates. These are outlined below and identify the AESI that were included on the 2020 MERS list for each category:

1. AESI that have been previously identified with immunization in general:
 - a. Anaphylaxis, thrombocytopenia, generalized convulsion
2. AESI associated with specific vaccine platforms:
 - a. Live vaccine: aseptic meningitis, encephalitis, myelitis
 - b. Modified vaccinia virus vector vaccine: myocarditis
 - c. Pandemic and some seasonal influenza vaccines: Guillain Barré Syndrome
3. AESI that may occur during the clinical course or as a complication of MERS infection due to viral replication or a host response immunopathogenic mechanism:
 - a. Acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS)
 - b. Pneumonitis
 - c. Encephalitis / Encephalomyelitis / ADEM
 - d. CNS vasculopathy (stroke)
 - e. Disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC)

- f. Enhanced disease following immunization
- g. Acute renal failure
- h. Maternal death, spontaneous abortion, stillbirth, neonatal death
- 4. Theoretical AESI based on animal models or in vitro experimental data:
 - a. Vaccine-associated enhanced disease seen in mouse model of MERS vaccines.

The initial landscape analysis for MERS AESI was completed in February 17, 2020 and was based on a non-systematic literature review of key review articles (link: <https://zenodo.org/records/6674510#.YxiiMOxBy3I>). Phase I or II clinical trials are projected to start for two MERS vaccine candidates in 2026 (Oxford MERS – ChAdOx1; IDT Biologika – MVA). Given the time since the first landscape analysis, an update was planned as part of SPEAC 2.0.

2. Objective of this deliverable

The primary objective was to conduct a scoping review of literature published after the previous landscape analysis to determine whether any new AESI should be added to the previous AESI list for novel MERS vaccines.

3. Methods

The literature search strategy focused on finding reviews of MERS disease published since the last landscape analysis which was completed in February 2020. The search was done by Matthew Dudleyon May 14, 2025 and included articles published on or after January 1, 2019. The specific strategy used was:

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("Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus"[Mesh] OR "Middle East Respiratory Syndrome"[ti] OR "MERS"[ti])
AND ("Clinical Trial"[Publication Type] OR "Review"[Publication Type] OR "Systematic Review"[Publication Type]
OR "Meta-Analysis"[Publication Type] OR "Clinical Trial Protocol"[Publication Type])
AND ("2019/01/01"[PDAT] : "3000/12/31"[PDAT])
AND English[lang]
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All identified articles were loaded into Covidence where review/summary article title/abstract were screened by one medical expert (B Law). Full text review was done subsequently, and relevant data extracted into Microsoft Word for the final set of included articles. The focus of the review was to include articles with a clinical focus (i.e., descriptive summaries of patient cases, or individual case details) that could identify new AESI not already included on the MERs AESI list. Additional references were identified from the citation lists of the primary review publications and retrieved for full text review. While screening articles in Covidence, tags were added for articles with content on geographical distribution of MERS, MERS-CoV virology and MERS-CoV vaccines. These are subjects included in the MERS dashboard prepared by the SPEAC digital transformation team. A list of the flagged articles was forwarded to the digital transformation team for review and decision as to whether any should be added to the MERS dashboard.

4. Results

A total of 485 articles were identified by the literature search. Figure 1 provides a PRISMA diagram for the search results. Title and abstract screening eliminated 325 articles. Among the 160 remaining articles, 75 were excluded after full text review and 85 included because of a clinical or pathogenesis focus with potential to inform the MERS AESI list or with relevance to the MERS digital dashboard (e.g., MERS geographic distribution, virology, vaccines). 42 articles were identified as relevant only for the MERS digital dashboard. An additional 10 articles were identified based on review of the citation list of included articles. Thus, data extraction into a Word document focused on any possible new AESI and was done for a total of 53 articles. A table in the Annex shows the MERS topics of interest for the 85 articles included for full text review. The full citations for the 160 articles included after title/abstract screening is provided in 4 different lists: A. 43 articles relevant to possible new AESI; B. 10 articles of interest identified from review of the included article citation lists; C. the 57 articles (15 of these were also among the 43 AESI relevant articles) with possible relevance for the MERS digital dashboard, which were also forwarded to the digital transformation team in charge of the dashboard; and D. the 85 articles excluded after title/abstract screening.

Figure 1. PRISMA Flow diagram for literature search for MERS virus priority AESI

The majority of the 43 included articles were reviews with no original data; however, 3 provided information on the incidence and mechanisms of acute kidney injury.⁵⁻⁷ The 10 articles identified from the citation lists had relevant data regarding acute kidney injury⁸, severe MERS disease including multiple organ dysfunction⁹⁻¹², the relevance of co-morbidities to severe MERS disease¹³⁻¹⁶ and myocarditis¹⁷. The evidence from each of these is summarized below.

Acute Kidney Injury (AKI)

Acute renal failure was listed on the first MERS landscape analysis AESI list from 2020. Many of the articles reviewed in this update mentioned acute kidney injury (AKI) as a frequent accompaniment to MERS. Since this is one component of multiple organ dysfunction syndrome (MODS) it was of interest to learn more about the frequency and causes of AKI in MERS. Unlike SARS-CoV-1 or SARS-CoV-2, which bind to ACE2 receptors, MERS binds to dipeptidyl-peptidase 4 (DDP4), which is abundantly expressed in the kidney as well as lung, small intestine, liver, prostate and immune cells.⁵ Zhou et al⁶ conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis to estimate the incidence of AKI in three severe coronavirus infections. Specifically, they found a much higher incidence in MERS (pooled estimate of 42.0% of cases with 95% confidence interval of 29.8-54.7%) than in SARS-CoV-1 (9.6%; 3.9-17.2%) and SARS-CoV-2 ~~COVID-19~~ (9.0%; 4.2-15.2%). Across all three pathogens, AKI significantly increased the risk of mortality (Odds Ratio 5.73; 95% confidence interval 3.75-8.77). Three studies assessed the potential causes of AKI in MERS.^{5, 7, 8} It is multifactorial involving a combination of pre-renal failure due to hypotension or dehydration, direct viral damage to the kidney, nephrotoxic medications, rhabdomyolysis, hypoxia as well as cytokine storm and multiple organ failure.

Severe MERS including Multiple Organ Dysfunction Syndrome (MODS)

Saad et al⁹ provided details on the course of 70 cases of MERS confirmed by RT-PCR and encountered at a single medical center in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia from October 1, 2012, to May 31, 2014. Hospitalization was required for 64 (91.4%), ICU admission for 49 (70%) mechanical ventilation for 46 (65.7%) and fatal outcome for 42 (60%). Clinical disease included ARDS in 28 (40%), AKI in 30 (42.9%), liver dysfunction in 22 (31.4%), arrhythmias in 11 (15.7%), DIC in 10 (14.3%), rhabdomyolysis in 10 (14.3%) and seizures in 6 (8.6%).

Al Ghamdhi et al¹⁰ summarized the hospital course of 51 PCR-confirmed MERS cases admitted to King Fahd General Hospital in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia from January through December 2014. There were 19 (37%) fatal cases. Respiratory symptoms predominated (90% shortness of breath, 80.4% cough, 33% hypoxia) but other organ systems were involved, including 21 (41.2%) with AKI (based on creatinine >1.5 mg/dL), 54.9% with leukopenia (WBC < 5000/mm³), 29.4% with thrombocytopenia (platelets <150,000 / uL), 27.5% anemia (hemoglobin < 10g/dL), 15.7% hypotension (BP <90/60), over 60% with evidence of acute liver injury (68.6% AST >40 U/L; 62.8% with LDH >300 U/L; 45.1% with ALT >50 IU/L) and 47.1% with elevated CK (>200 U/L).

Ebrahim et al¹¹ summarized 501 confirmed MERS cases admitted to one of four Saudi Arabia centers from April 2014 to Nov 12, 2019. 169 (33.7%) were admitted directly to the Intensive Care Unit (ICU). Organ systems involved included lungs (63.7% abnormal chest X ray), brain (26.1% abnormal brain MRI), hematologic (49.3% anemia, 21.7% leukopenia, 26.4% thrombocytopenia), liver (elevated: LDH in 88.4%, AST in 67.1%, ALT in 33.2%; bilirubin in 12.4%), kidney (18.4% elevated creatinine) and coagulation system (prolonged PT in 26.5%, elevated aPTT in 22.7%). A notable feature of this study was the high prevalence of other infections, with 116 (25.9%) of all cases with positive blood cultures and 105 (23.5%) of all cases with urinary tract infections.

The largest reported experience with MERS outside of the Middle East was by Choi et al¹² who reported on 186 confirmed MERS-CoV infections requiring hospitalization in Korea. The percentage of patients with laboratory abnormalities on admission to hospital included: 56.8% with hypoxia based on a PaO₂:FiO₂ ratio of <300; 42.1% with leukopenia (< 4000 WBC/ml); 46.6% with thrombocytopenia (<150,000/uL); 49.7% with elevated AST (>40 IU/L); and 5.2% with elevated creatinine (>1.5mg/dL). Over the course of their disease, 20.7% developed ARDS, 14.0% AKI and 13.4% shock. 24.2% required mechanical ventilation, 7% ECMO and 20.4% died.

Based on the above, MERS is a severe disease with a high likelihood of admission to hospital, requirement for intensive care, fatal outcome and multiple organ dysfunction and, to a lesser extent, multiple organ failure.

Risk factors for severe MERS disease

Badawi et al¹³ did a systematic review to estimate the prevalence of comorbidities in severe MERS infections. Their meta-analysis was based on 12 studies with 637 confirmed cases including 427 males and 210 females. The mean age was 53 (standard error of 3 years; range 36-66 years). Study population size ranged from 5 to 261. Most cases were from the Middle East, in particular Saudi Arabia, but they also included a few from European countries (France, Germany, Italy, UK) as well as Jordan and Tunisia. The pooled estimates for prevalence (95% confidence interval) of comorbidities were: diabetes mellitus – 51% (36-66%); hypertension 48% (31-65%); cardiac diseases 31% (20-41%); and obesity 16% (12-19%). They speculated that comorbidities could contribute to severe MERS disease via several mechanisms including endothelial dysfunction, proinflammatory state, attenuation of innate immune responses, and impaired macrophage and lymphocyte functions.

Two studies not included in Badawi et al's meta-analysis summarized above also found a high proportion of comorbidities among severe cases. Almekhlafie et al¹⁴ utilized the same group of 70 patients with confirmed MERS as described above for Saad et al. but focused on the 31 cases admitted to their local ICU unit as a marker of severe MERS (18 other ICU cases reported by Saad et al were admitted to different ICUs within the same hospital complex). The 31 ICU patients had a mean age of 59 (SD 20) and 71% were male. At least 1 comorbid condition was found in 87.1% of cases and the median number of comorbidities prior to hospital admission was 3 (IQR 2-4). Concomitant infection was documented in 58.1% by deep tracheal aspirates and 12.9% by positive blood culture. Garout et al¹⁵ studied 52 ICU cases and found that 51.9% had diabetes, 46.2% hypertension, and 21.2% chronic renal failure.

Banik et al¹⁶ used an online Saudi database of reported cases (n=1,060 as of Oct 11, 2015) to assess comorbidities as risk factors for fatal MERS (384 of 1060 cases; 36% mortality). Significant risk factors that increased the likelihood of death (Odds Ratio; {95% Confidence Interval}) included: malignancy 9.4 (2.1-42.8); Diabetes mellitus 2.8 (1.6-5); kidney disease 3.9 (1.8-8.3); and Hypertension 2.1 (1.1-3.7). Concomitant heart, lung, or neurologic disease did not increase the risk of fatal outcome.

Myocarditis in MERS

Among all studies included for this landscape update there was only a single case of myocarditis reported.¹⁷ This involved a 60-year-old man who was RT-PCR positive for MERS-CoV (sputum sample). He presented with left sided chest pain and investigations on admission revealed elevated troponin I (1.13 ug/L; normal range 0-0.4 ug/L) and pro-brain natriuretic peptide (6000 pg/ml; normal <100 pg/ml). By day 2 in hospital the latter had increased to 8906 pg/ml. Electrocardiogram showed sinus tachycardia (120 beats/minute) and diffuse T wave inversion. Transthoracic echocardiography showed severe global left ventricular systolic dysfunction and a small

pericardial effusion. The differential diagnoses included myopericarditis, ischemic cardiomyopathy, and stress-induced cardiomyopathy. A cardiac MRI was most consistent with myocarditis showing myocardial edema and late gadolinium enhancement. The impaired left ventricular function was followed using echocardiograms and lasted for 3 months. The Brighton case definition for myocarditis was not applied but based on the case details this would meet LOC 1 of diagnostic certainty based on the combination of elevated Troponin I and typical abnormal cardiac MRI as well as the echocardiographic abnormality. Of note, a thorough investigation of other viral causes was done, and nothing found despite testing for influenza, parainfluenza, adenovirus, coxsackie B virus, parvovirus B19, echovirus, EBV, CMV, Hepatitis C and HIV. Further blood culture for bacterial pathogens was negative.

Updated AESI list Related to MERS disease

After completing the scoping review for MERS disease presentation and complications it is concluded there is no reason to add anything to the previous AESI list. Specifically, while severe MERS disease presenting as multiple organ dysfunction was a consideration, the clear association with underlying comorbidities made it impossible to ascribe to MERS infection alone. Aside from comorbidities, severe ARDS, which is a hallmark feature of MERS, can lead to multiple organ dysfunctions. Other mechanisms of multiple organ dysfunction that could be operative in MERS include complications of prolonged mechanical ventilation or ECMO, sepsis occurring in an ICU setting, and drug-based complications.

The single case of myocarditis was compelling in terms of it meeting the Brighton case definition at a Level 1 of diagnostic certainty and the absence of any other explanation despite a thorough investigation for other infectious causes. However, a single case out of all the thousands of MERS cases reported to date is an insufficient reason to add it to the AESI list.

There were some updates to the AESI included on the 2020 MERS list.

Table 1 presents the MERS AESI list focusing on those related to MERS disease only based on immunopathogenesis, viral replication, or both.

Relative to the 2020 MERS list, some AESI have been clarified. Encephalopathy has been deleted as a separate AESI because it is part of both encephalitis and ADEM. CNS vasculopathy presenting as stroke was on the first AESI list but in the update is represented as Thrombosis and thromboembolism since there is a Brighton case definition and Companion Guide for that and both include stroke due to venous or arterial thrombosis. Acute renal failure has been replaced by acute kidney injury, which is clearly a common feature in MERS disease, albeit with multiple possible mechanisms due to viral infection, immunopathogenesis or prerenal problems including hypotension, sepsis, cytokine storm and hypoxia.

Finally, this update did not include special populations (pregnant women, fetus, newborn, pediatric and immunocompromised). These are being covered by the SPEAC team working on special populations, and separate guidance is being provided.

TABLE 1. AESI RELEVANT TO MERS VIRUS DISEASE

Body System	AESI	Theoretical Basis for Including AESI		Brighton CD	Brighton CD Companion Guide
		MERS disease immunopathogenesis	MERS viral replication		
Neurologic	Encephalitis	✓	✓	YES	YES
	Acute disseminated encephalomyelitis (ADEM)	✓		YES	YES
Hematologic	Disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC)	✓	✓	NO*	NO*
	Thrombosis and thromboembolism	✓	✓	YES	YES
Immunologic	Vaccine-associated enhanced disease	✓	✓	YES	YES
Kidney	Acute kidney injury (AKI)	✓	✓	NO*	NO*
Respiratory	Acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS)	✓	✓	YES	YES
	Pneumonitis	✓	✓	NO*	NO*

* SPEAC has no plans to develop specific case definitions for these AESI, however, all will be covered in terms of evidence for dysfunction as part of the acute Multiple Organ Dysfunction Syndrome (MODS) which is currently under development and will be completed in 2026.

5. Recommendations & discussion

Table 2 presents the full list of AESI that could occur following candidate MERS virus vaccination. The AESI listed have been arranged by whether or not they are theoretically possible to occur with:

- I. Any vaccine based on host immune response (anaphylaxis, thrombocytopenia, GBS) or vaccine reactogenicity (generalized convulsive seizure);
- II. Any vaccine designed to target MERS virus (based on MERS disease immunopathogenesis);
- III. Live-attenuated MERS virus vaccines (based on complications due to MERS virus replication). Live attenuated vaccines differ in the degree to which they replicate in the human body as well as in the potential to revert to a version that may behave more like the wild type virus. Pre-clinical and clinical trial data will inform as to the potential likelihood that viral replication could occur and lead to an adverse event; or
- IV. Specific vaccine platforms (based on demonstrated platform-AESI association).

It is acknowledged that all listed AESI are rare and unlikely to be observed in Phase I or II trials. Still, any may occur, and given the associated morbidity and potential for public concern, SPEAC recommends a standard approach to the listed AESI in terms of identifying, investigating, classifying (i.e., meeting or not meeting a case definition) and reporting.

Protocol-specified AESI are defined as those for which an association has been demonstrated with the same or a similar vaccine platform or the antigen(s) included in the vaccine. SPEAC recommends that developers provide

specific plans in the protocol and associated documents, as needed, for the approach to all protocol-specified AESIs. Based on existing Brighton case definitions and Companion Guides, SPEAC is developing tools that can assist developers in their protocol plans for the AESI. These could include conducting surveillance during the clinical trial, training site investigators, investigating any possible occurrences (including special laboratory testing, if indicated, which could be remote from the study site), and plans for follow-up assessments, reporting and MedDRA coding.

Other AESI in Table 2 below are considered theoretical possibilities that could occur with any vaccine, or that are predicted based on MERS disease immunopathogenesis. As with protocol-specified AESI, the events are rare and unlikely to occur in early phases of clinical trials. Despite that, SPEAC recommends that a standard approach be taken to such events so that there is consistency in identifying, classifying and reporting them. This recommendation is aligned with CIOMS VI¹⁸, which noted “Medical and scientific judgement should be exercised in deciding whether expedited reporting is appropriate in...” non-SAE situations.

SPEAC recommendations clearly do not supplant or replace regulatory obligations. Further, developers may decide to specify more AESI in their clinical protocols than are recommended in Table 2 below. Rather, it is intended that SPEAC supports developers in taking a standard approach to the listed AESI by providing tools, including Case Definitions, Companion Guides (that contain background incidence rates, risk factors, data collection forms and algorithms for assigning level of diagnostic certainty), online capacity for automated Brighton Classification, and dashboards for background incidence, evidence on vaccine-AESI associations and non-vaccine AESI risk factors. Further, SPEAC is currently developing additional tools (symptom checklists, AESI laboratory/imaging checklist to determine site capacity for investigating possible AESI and assigning level 1, 2 or 3 diagnostic certainty) to aid clinical trial sites in recognizing and investigating possible AESI.

TABLE 2. SPEAC recommendations for handling theoretically possible AESI according to vaccine type. AESI list for a given vaccine candidate will include all AESIs listed under I and II as well as those for the specific platform, as appropriate (III & IV). Wherever a Table cell does not have "YES", it means "NO"

Vaccine type		I. All vaccines	II All MERS Vaccines	III. Live MERS Vaccines	IV. Specific Vaccine Platforms	
Theoretical Basis for AESI		Host immune response or vaccine reactogenicity	MERS disease immuno-pathogenesis	MERS virus replication	ChAdOx1	MVA
Body System	AESI	SPEAC Recommendation for AESI				
		Adopt standard approach to investigation and classification, IF occurs as an AEFI			Specify in Trial Protocol	
Hematologic	Thrombocytopenia	YES			YES	
	Thrombosis and thromboembolism		YES	YES		
	TTS-VITT				YES	
	DIC		YES	YES		
Immunologic	Anaphylaxis	YES				
	VAED		YES ¹			
Neurologic	Generalized convulsive seizure	YES ²		YES ³		

	ADEM		YES		YES	
	Encephalitis			YES ⁴		
	Transverse Myelitis ^{&}				YES	
	GBS [#]	YES [#]			YES	
Respiratory	ARDS		YES ⁴	YES ⁴		
	Pneumonitis			YES		

[&] Transverse myelitis with demyelination as opposed to acute infectious myelitis.

[#] GBS has been associated with some seasonal influenza vaccines, monovalent H1N1 pandemic vaccine and COVID-19 ChAdOx-1 S vaccine. It is included in the ‘all vaccines’ column because it has an immunogenic pathogenesis and so is theoretically possible with any vaccine.

¹⁻⁴ Exceptions to table recommendations:

¹ Should be Protocol-specified if pre-clinical data (in vitro or animal models) or nature of human immune response raises the possibility of vaccine-associated enhanced disease.

² Should be Protocol-specified if vaccine highly reactogenic in terms of febrile response within the first few days following immunization, especially if target population includes children < 6 years old

³ Should be Protocol-specified if fever occurs during the known period of vaccine strain viremia (based on animal or clinical data), especially if target population includes children < 6 years old.

⁴ Should be Protocol-specified if vaccine strain shown to be neurotropic based on pre-clinical or human clinical trials.

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13. Badawi A, Ryoo SG. Prevalence of comorbidities in the Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV): a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int JID* 2016; 49: 129-133
14. Almekhlafie GA, Albarrak MM, Mandurah Y et al. Presentation and outcome of the MERS in Saudi intensive care unit patients. *Critical Care*. 2016; 20:123. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13054-0160-1303-8> PMID 27153800
15. Garout MA, Jokhdar HAA, Aljahdali IA et al. Mortality rate of ICU patients with the middle east respiratory syndrome – coronavirus infection at King Fahad Hospital, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. *Centr Eur J Public Health* 2018; 26(2): 87-91. <https://doi.org/10.21101/cejph.a4764>
16. Banik GR, Alqahtani AS, Booy R, Rashid H. Risk factors for severity and mortality in patients with MERS-CoV: Analysis of publicly available data from Saudi Arabia. *Virologica Sinica* 2016; 31(1): 81-84. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12250-015-3679-z>
17. Alhogbani T. Acute myocarditis associated with novel MERS coronavirus. *Ann Saudi Med* 2016; 36(1): 78-80. <https://doi.org/10.5144/0256-4947.2016.78>
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ANNEXES

Annex 1

List of All articles Reviewed for the MERS Landscape Review

TABLE 1.1. 85 articles retrieved from literature search classified by year published and topic area of interest (marked by 'YES'). All 43 with clinical content or a focus on pathogenesis had full text review for possible relevance to MERS disease AESI. OF 57 with possible relevance for the MERS digital dashboard topics (18 geographic distribution, 16 virology and 36 vaccine), 42 did not have full text review because there was nothing relevant to AESI. All 57 were forwarded to the digital team for consideration of inclusion in the MERS dashboard. First authors of articles cited in the landscape update are in bold text and the citation number is shown. Full citation for all articles provided below the table. Wherever a Table cell does not have "YES", it means "NO".

Year Published	First Author	Topic Focus of Interest			
		Clinical Content re Possible AESI	Geographic Distribution*	Virology*	Vaccine*
2025	Karani	YES	YES	YES	
	Khatun	YES (pathogenesis)			
	Link				YES
	Raadsen				YES
	Tanneti	YES (pathogenesis)			
2024	Saloman	YES	YES		
	Shrwani	YES			YES
2023	Islam A		YES		
	Kandeel				YES
	Kovalenko				YES
	Minchin				YES
	Pustake			YES	
	Tambe LAM		YES		
2022	Alsafi	YES		YES	
	Bosaeed				YES
	Choi				YES
	Costanzo				YES
	Gartian	YES			YES
	Goyal	YES		YES	
	Irani	YES			
	Lin				YES
	Peiris		YES		
	Pustake	YES			
	Qiao			YES	
Suaifan				YES	

	Tai				YES
	Wang	YES			
	Xiang				YES
	Yan		YES		
	Yong				YES
2021	Al Tawfiq	YES	YES		YES
	Anjum	YES (pathogenesis)			
	Begum				YES
	Berber		YES		
	Cevik	YES		YES	
	Li	YES			
	Liu	YES (Pathogenesis)			
	Lombardi	YES			
	Low			YES	
	Maury	YES			
	Molaei				YES
	Motavalli	YES			
	Nascimento				YES
	Noor	YES (Pathogenesis)			
	Rabaan ^{COV196}	YES	YES	YES	
	Rabaan ^{COV94}			YES	
	Ryabkova	YES			
	Sanguedolce	YES			
	Sessa	YES			
	Yu				YES
Zhou	YES				
2020	Al-Tawfiq	YES			
	Bleibtreu	YES			
	Chasouraki	YES			
	Chen ^{Signal Trans Targ Ther}			YES	YES
	Da Costa	YES	YES	YES	
	Di Maria			YES	
	Folegatti				YES
	Gergesharb	YES			
	Giannis	YES			
	Golke			YES	
	Gulati	YES			
	Hashemzadeh				YES
	Huang		YES		YES
	Koch				YES
	Kukla	YES			
	Labetoulle	YES	YES		YES
	Li ^{J Biomed Sci}				YES
	Masood	YES	YES	YES	
McFee	YES	YES			

	Memish	YES	YES	YES	YES
	Mostafa	YES	YES	YES	YES
	Xu <small>Eur Rev Med Pharm Sci</small>	YES			
2019	Fung	YES (Pathogenesis)			
	Gardner		YES		
	Modjarrad				YES
	Mubarak	YES (Pathogenesis)			YES
	Roberts				YES
	Schindewolf				YES
	Shokri	YES (Pathogenesis)			
	Sikkema		YES		
	Song	YES (Pathogenesis)			
	Xu				YES
	Yong				YES
	Zhou				YES
Total included articles with relevance to topic:		43	18	16	36

Literature Search Citations

A. Articles with clinical content that could possibly inform the AESI list. Of the 43 listed below, 15 also had possible relevance for the digital dashboard and are included in List C. There was a lot of repetition among the articles and only a few are cited in the landscape analysis. These are bolded in the list below.

- 1 Al-Tawfiq JA, Azhar EI, Memish ZA, Zumla A. Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus. *Semin Respir Crit Care Med.* 2021;42(6):828-38.
- 2 Al-Tawfiq JA, Memish ZA. Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus. *Semin Respir Crit Care Med.* 2020;41(4):568-78.
- 3 Alsafi RT. Lessons from SARS-CoV, MERS-CoV, and SARS-CoV-2 Infections: What We Know So Far. *Can J Infect Dis Med Microbiol.* 2022;2022:1156273.
- 4 Anjum FR, Anam S, Abbas G, Mahmood MS, Rahman SU, Goraya MU, et al. Type I IFNs: A Blessing in Disguise or Partner in Crime in MERS-CoV-, SARS-CoV-, and SARS-CoV-2-Induced Pathology and Potential Use of Type I IFNs in Synergism with IFN- γ as a Novel Antiviral Approach Against COVID-19. *Viral Immunol.* 2021;34(5):321-9.
- 5 Bleibtreu A, Bertine M, Bertin C, Houhou-Fidouh N, Visseaux B. Focus on Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV). *Med Mal Infect.* 2020;50(3):243-51.
- 6 Cevik M, Tate M, Lloyd O, Maraolo AE, Schafers J, Ho A. SARS-CoV-2, SARS-CoV, and MERS-CoV viral load dynamics, duration of viral shedding, and infectiousness: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Lancet Microbe.* 2021;2(1):e13-e22.
- 7 Chasouraki AM, Violetis OA, Abdelrasoul M, Tsagalou EP. Acute Myocarditis Related to COVID-19: Comparison to SARS and MERS. *SN Compr Clin Med.* 2020;2(12):2684-90.
- 8 da Costa VG, Moreli ML, Saivish MV. The emergence of SARS, MERS and novel SARS-2 coronaviruses in the 21st century. *Arch Virol.* 2020;165(7):1517-26.
- 9 Fung TS, Liu DX. Human Coronavirus: Host-Pathogen Interaction. *Annu Rev Microbiol.* 2019;73:529-57.
- 10 Gartlan C, Tipton T, Salguero FJ, Sattentau Q, Gorringer A, Carroll MW. Vaccine-Associated Enhanced Disease and Pathogenic Human Coronaviruses. *Front Immunol.* 2022;13:882972.

- 11 Gerges Harb J, Noureldine HA, Chedid G, Eldine MN, Abdallah DA, Chedid NF, et al. SARS, MERS and COVID-19: clinical manifestations and organ-system complications: a mini review. *Pathog Dis.* 2020;78(4).
- 12 Giannis D, Ziogas IA, Gianni P. Coagulation disorders in coronavirus infected patients: COVID-19, SARS-CoV-1, MERS-CoV and lessons from the past. *J Clin Virol.* 2020;127:104362.
- 13 Goyal R, Gautam RK, Chopra H, Dubey AK, Singla RK, Rayan RA, et al. Comparative highlights on MERS-CoV, SARS-CoV-1, SARS-CoV-2, and NEO-CoV. *EXCLI J.* 2022;21:1245-72.
- 14 Gulati A, Pomeranz C, Qamar Z, Thomas S, Frisch D, George G, et al. A Comprehensive Review of Manifestations of Novel Coronaviruses in the Context of Deadly COVID-19 Global Pandemic. *Am J Med Sci.* 2020;360(1):5-34.
- 15 Irani S. Immune Responses in SARS-CoV-2, SARS-CoV, and MERS-CoV Infections: A Comparative Review. *Int J Prev Med.* 2022;13:45.
- 16 Karani A, Ombok C, Situma S, Breiman R, Mureithi M, Jaoko W, et al. Low-Level Zoonotic Transmission of Clade C MERS-CoV in Africa: Insights from Scoping Review and Cohort Studies in Hospital and Community Settings. *Viruses.* 2025;17(1).
- 17 Khatun O, Kaur S, Tripathi S. Anti-interferon armamentarium of human coronaviruses. *Cell Mol Life Sci.* 2025;82(1):116.
- 18 Kukla M, Skonieczna-Żydecka K, Kotfis K, Maciejewska D, Łoniewski I, Lara LF, et al. COVID-19, MERS and SARS with Concomitant Liver Injury-Systematic Review of the Existing Literature. *J Clin Med.* 2020;9(5).
- 19 Labetoulle R, Detoc M, Gagnaire J, Berthelot P, Pelissier C, Fontana L, et al. COVID-19 in health-care workers: lessons from SARS and MERS epidemics and perspectives for chemoprophylaxis and vaccines. *Expert Rev Vaccines.* 2020;19(10):937-47.
- 20 Li CH, Chiou HC, Lin MH, Kuo CH, Lin YC, Hung CH. Immunological map in COVID-19. *J Microbiol Immunol Infect.* 2021;54(4):547-56.
- 21 Liu T, Feng M, Wen Z, He Y, Lin W, Zhang M. Comparison of the Characteristics of Cytokine Storm and Immune Response Induced by SARS-CoV, MERS-CoV, and SARS-CoV-2 Infections. *J Inflamm Res.* 2021;14:5475-87.
- 22 Lombardi AF, Afsahi AM, Gupta A, Gholamrezanezhad A. Severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS), Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS), influenza, and COVID-19, beyond the lungs: a review article. *Radiol Med.* 2021;126(4):561-9.
- 23 Masood N, Malik SS, Raja MN, Mubarak S, Yu C. Unraveling the Epidemiology, Geographical Distribution, and Genomic Evolution of Potentially Lethal Coronaviruses (SARS, MERS, and SARS CoV-2). *Front Cell Infect Microbiol.* 2020;10:499.
- 24 Maury A, Lyoubi A, Peiffer-Smadja N, de Broucker T, Meppiel E. Neurological manifestations associated with SARS-CoV-2 and other coronaviruses: A narrative review for clinicians. *Rev Neurol (Paris).* 2021;177(1-2):51-64.
- 25 McFee RB. Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) Coronavirus. *Dis Mon.* 2020;66(9):101053.
- 26 Memish ZA, Perlman S, Van Kerkhove MD, Zumla A. Middle East respiratory syndrome. *Lancet.* 2020;395(10229):1063-77.
- 27 Mostafa A, Kandeil A, Shehata M, El Shesheny R, Samy AM, Kayali G, et al. Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus (MERS-CoV): State of the Science. *Microorganisms.* 2020;8(7).
- 28 Motavalli R, Abdelbasset WK, Rahman HS, Achmad MH, Sergeevna NK, Zekiy AO, et al. The lethal internal face of the coronaviruses: Kidney tropism of the SARS, MERS, and COVID19 viruses. *IUBMB Life.* 2021;73(8):1005-15.
- 29 Mubarak A, Alturaiki W, Hemida MG. Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus (MERS-CoV): Infection, Immunological Response, and Vaccine Development. *J Immunol Res.* 2019;2019:6491738.
- 30 Noor R. A comparative review of pathogenesis and host innate immunity evasion strategies among the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), severe acute respiratory syndrome

- coronavirus (SARS-CoV) and the Middle East respiratory syndrome coro. Arch Microbiol. 2021;203(5):1943-51.
- 31 Pustake M, Tambolkar I, Giri P, Gandhi C. SARS, MERS and CoVID-19: An overview and comparison of clinical, laboratory and radiological features. J Family Med Prim Care. 2022;11(1):10-7.
 - 32 Rabaan AA, Al-Ahmed SH, Sah R, Alqumber MA, Haque S, Patel SK, et al. MERS-CoV: epidemiology, molecular dynamics, therapeutics, and future challenges. Ann Clin Microbiol Antimicrob. 2021;20(1):8.
 - 33 Ryabkova VA, Churilov LP, Shoefeld Y. Influenza infection, SARS, MERS and COVID-19: Cytokine storm - The common denominator and the lessons to be learned. Clin Immunol. 2021;223:108652.
 - 34 Salomon I. Saudi Arabia's Middle East respiratory syndrome Coronavirus (MERS-CoV) outbreak: consequences, reactions, and takeaways. Ann Med Surg (Lond). 2024;86(8):4668-74.
 - 35 Sanguedolce F, Zanelli M, Froio E, Bisagni A, Zizzo M, Ascani S, et al. Pathological diagnosis of Coronavirus-related nephropathy: insight from postmortem studies. Crit Rev Clin Lab Sci. 2021;58(8):563-75.
 - 36 Sessa F, Salerno M, Pomara C. Autopsy Tool in Unknown Diseases: The Experience with Coronaviruses (SARS-CoV, MERS-CoV, SARS-CoV-2). Medicina (Kaunas). 2021;57(4).
 - 37 Shokri S, Mahmoudvand S, Taherkhani R, Farshadpour F. Modulation of the immune response by Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus. J Cell Physiol. 2019;234(3):2143-51.
 - 38 Shrwani KJ, Mahallawi WH, Mohana AI, Algaissi A, Dhayhi N, Sharwani NJ, et al. Mucosal immunity in upper and lower respiratory tract to MERS-CoV. Front Immunol. 2024;15:1358885.
 - 39 Song Z, Xu Y, Bao L, Zhang L, Yu P, Qu Y, et al. From SARS to MERS, Thrusting Coronaviruses into the Spotlight. Viruses. 2019;11(1).
 - 40 Tanneti NS, Stillwell HA, Weiss SR. Human coronaviruses: activation and antagonism of innate immune responses. Microbiol Mol Biol Rev. 2025;89(1):e0001623.
 - 41 Wang F, Suo XG, Wang C, Wang JN, He XY, Wang FC, et al. Highly pathogenic coronaviruses and the kidney. Biomed Pharmacother. 2022;156:113807.
 - 42 Xu P, Sun GD, Li ZZ. Clinical characteristics of two human-to-human transmitted coronaviruses: Corona Virus Disease 2019 vs. Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus. Eur Rev Med Pharmacol Sci. 2020;24(10):5797-809.
 - 43 Zhou S, Xu J, Xue C, Yang B, Mao Z, Ong ACM. Coronavirus-associated kidney outcomes in COVID-19, SARS, and MERS: a meta-analysis and systematic review. Ren Fail. 2021; 43(1):1-15.

B. 10 articles found by search of included articles citations. All of the articles below are cited in the landscape analysis.

- 1 Egbi OG, Adejumo OA, Akinbodewa AA. Coronavirus infection and kidney disease: a review of current and emerging evidence. Pan Afr Med J 2020; 37:149. <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2020.37.149.23655>
- 2 Saad M, Omrani AS, Baig K et al. Clinical aspects and outcomes of 70 patients with MERS coronavirus infection: a single center experience in Saudi Arabia. Int JID 2014; 29:301-6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2014.09.003>
- 3 Al Ghamdi KM, Ghandoorra Y et al. Treatment outcomes for patients with MERS coronavirus (MERS CoV) infection at a coronavirus referral center in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. BMC Infectious diseases 2016; 16:174. <https://doi/10.1186/s12879-016-1492-4 PMID 28056850>
- 4 Ebrahim SH, Maher AD, Kanagasabai U et al. MERS-CoV Confirmation among 6873 suspected persons and relevant Epidemiologic and Clinical Features Saudi Arabia 2014-2019. EClinicalMedicine 2021; 41:101191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eclinm.2021.101191>
- 5 Choi WS, Kang CI, Kim Y et al. Clinical presentation and outcomes of MERS in the Republic of Korea. Infect Chemother 2016; 48:118-26. <https://doi.org/10.3947/ic.2016.48.2.118>
- 6 Badawi A, Ryoo SG. Prevalence of comorbidities in the Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV): a systematic review and meta-analysis. Int JID 2016; 49: 129-133

- 7 Almekhlafie GA, Albarrak MM, Mandurah Y et al. Presentation and outcome of the MERS in Saudi intensive care unit patients. *Critical Care*. 2016; 20:123. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13054-0160-1303-8> PMID [27153800](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27153800/)
- 8 Garout MA, Jokhdar HAA, Aljahdali IA et al. Mortality rate of ICU patients with the middle east respiratory syndrome – coronavirus infection at King Fahad Hospital, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. *Centr Eur J Public Health* 2018; 26(2): 87-91. <https://doi.org/10.21101/ceiph.a4764>
- 9 Banik GR, Alqahtani AS, Booy R, Rashid H. Risk factors for severity and mortality in patients with MERS-CoV: Analysis of publicly available data from Saudi arabia. *Virologica Sinica* 2016; 31(1): 81-84. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12250-015-3679-z>
- 10 Alhogbani T. Acute myocarditis associated with novel MERS coronavirus. *Ann Saudi Med* 2016; 36(1): 78-80 <https://doi.org/10.5144/0256-4947.2016.78>

C. 57 articles with relevance to digital dashboard topics of MERS geographic distribution, virology or vaccines. 42 articles had relevance for the dashboard only, whereas 15 had clinical content possibly relevant to AESIs and so are included in List A. These 15 are bolded in the list below.

- 1 Al-Tawfiq JA, Azhar EI, Memish ZA, Zumla A. Middle East Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus. *Semin Respir Crit Care Med*. 2021;42(6):828-38.
- 2 Alsafi RT. Lessons from SARS-CoV, MERS-CoV, and SARS-CoV-2 Infections: What We Know So Far. *Can J Infect Dis Med Microbiol*. 2022;2022:1156273.
- 3 Begum J, Mir NA, Dev K, Buyamayum B, Wani MY, Raza M. Challenges and prospects of COVID-19 vaccine development based on the progress made in SARS and MERS vaccine development. *Transbound Emerg Dis*. 2021;68(3):1111-24.
- 4 Berber E, Sumbria D, Çanakoğlu N. Meta-analysis and comprehensive study of coronavirus outbreaks: SARS, MERS and COVID-19. *J Infect Public Health*. 2021;14(8):1051-64.
- 5 Bosaeed M, Balkhy HH, Almaziad S, Aljami HA, Alhatmi H, Alanazi H, et al. Safety and immunogenicity of ChAdOx1 MERS vaccine candidate in healthy Middle Eastern adults (MERS002): an open-label, non-randomised, dose-escalation, phase 1b trial. *Lancet Microbe*. 2022;3(1):e11-e20.
- 6 Cevik M, Tate M, Lloyd O, Maraolo AE, Schafers J, Ho A. SARS-CoV-2, SARS-CoV, and MERS-CoV viral load dynamics, duration of viral shedding, and infectiousness: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Lancet Microbe*. 2021;2(1):e13-e22.
- 7 Chen B, Tian EK, He B, Tian L, Han R, Wang S, et al. Overview of lethal human coronaviruses. *Signal Transduct Target Ther*. 2020;5(1):89.
- 8 Choi JA, Kim JO. Middle East Respiratory Syndrome coronavirus vaccine development: updating clinical studies using platform technologies. *J Microbiol*. 2022;60(3):238-46.
- 9 Costanzo M, De Giglio MAR, Roviello GN. Anti-Coronavirus Vaccines: Past Investigations on SARS-CoV-1 and MERS-CoV, the Approved Vaccines from BioNTech/Pfizer, Moderna, Oxford/AstraZeneca and others under Development Against SARSCoV- 2 Infection. *Curr Med Chem*. 2022;29(1):4-18.
- 10 da Costa VG, Moreli ML, Saivish MV. The emergence of SARS, MERS and novel SARS-2 coronaviruses in the 21st century. *Arch Virol*. 2020;165(7):1517-26.
- 11 Di Maria E, Latini A, Borgiani P, Novelli G. Genetic variants of the human host influencing the coronavirus-associated phenotypes (SARS, MERS and COVID-19): rapid systematic review and field synopsis. *Hum Genomics*. 2020;14(1):30.
- 12 Folegatti PM, Bittaye M, Flaxman A, Lopez FR, Bellamy D, Kupke A, et al. Safety and immunogenicity of a candidate Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus viral-vectored vaccine: a dose-escalation, open-label, non-randomised, uncontrolled, phase 1 trial. *Lancet Infect Dis*. 2020;20(7):816-26.
- 13 Gardner EG, Kelton D, Poljak Z, von Dobschuetz S, Greer AL. A rapid scoping review of Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus in animal hosts. *Zoonoses Public Health*. 2019;66(1):35-46.

- 14 Gartlan C, Tipton T, Salguero FJ, Sattentau Q, Gorringe A, Carroll MW. Vaccine-Associated Enhanced Disease and Pathogenic Human Coronaviruses. *Front Immunol.* 2022;13:882972.
- 15 Golke A, Piekarska K, Dzieciatkowski T. Coronaviruses - a new old menace. *Postepy Biochem.* 2020;66(4):303-8.
- 16 Goyal R, Gautam RK, Chopra H, Dubey AK, Singla RK, Rayan RA, et al. Comparative highlights on MERS-CoV, SARS-CoV-1, SARS-CoV-2, and NEO-CoV. *EXCLI J.* 2022;21:1245-72.
- 17 Hashemzadeh A, Avan A, Ferns GA, Khazaei M. Vaccines based on virus-like nano-particles for use against Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) coronavirus. *Vaccine.* 2020;38(36):5742-6.
- 18 Huang AT, Garcia-Carreras B, Hitchings MDT, Yang B, Katzelnick LC, Rattigan SM, et al. A systematic review of antibody mediated immunity to coronaviruses: kinetics, correlates of protection, and association with severity. *Nat Commun.* 2020;11(1):4704.
- 19 Islam MM, Khanom H, Farag E, Mim ZT, Naidoo P, Mkhize-Kwitshana ZL, et al. Global patterns of Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV) prevalence and seroprevalence in camels: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *One Health.* 2023;16:100561.
- 20 Kandeel M, Morsy MA, Abd El-Lateef HM, Marzok M, El-Beltagi HS, Al Khodair KM, et al. Safety and immunogenicity of the ChAdOx1, MVA-MERS-S, and GLS-5300 DNA MERS-CoV vaccines. *Int Immunopharmacol.* 2023;118:109998.
- 21 Karani A, Ombok C, Situma S, Breiman R, Mureithi M, Jaoko W, et al. Low-Level Zoonotic Transmission of Clade C MERS-CoV in Africa: Insights from Scoping Review and Cohort Studies in Hospital and Community Settings. *Viruses.* 2025;17(1).
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- 23 Kovalenko A, Ryabchevskaya E, Evtushenko E, Nikitin N, Karpova O. Recombinant Protein Vaccines against Human Betacoronaviruses: Strategies, Approaches and Progress. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2023;24(2).
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- 25 Li YD, Chi WY, Su JH, Ferrall L, Hung CF, Wu TC. Coronavirus vaccine development: from SARS and MERS to COVID-19. *J Biomed Sci.* 2020;27(1):104.
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- 28 Low ZY, Yip AJW, Sharma A, Lal SK. SARS coronavirus outbreaks past and present-a comparative analysis of SARS-CoV-2 and its predecessors. *Virus Genes.* 2021;57(4):307-17.
- 29 Masood N, Malik SS, Raja MN, Mubarik S, Yu C. Unraveling the Epidemiology, Geographical Distribution, and Genomic Evolution of Potentially Lethal Coronaviruses (SARS, MERS, and SARS CoV-2). *Front Cell Infect Microbiol.* 2020;10:499.
- 30 McFee RB. Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) Coronavirus. *Dis Mon.* 2020;66(9):101053.
- 31 Memish ZA, Perlman S, Van Kerkhove MD, Zumla A. Middle East respiratory syndrome. *Lancet.* 2020;395(10229):1063-77.
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- 39 Qiao S, Zhang S, Ge J, Wang X. The spike glycoprotein of highly pathogenic human coronaviruses: structural insights for understanding infection, evolution and inhibition. *FEBS Open Bio.* 2022;12(9):1602-22.
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